

Synthesis and Pharmacological Screening of some New 2-Thio-3-(substituted-aminomethyl)-5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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The pharmacological significance of oxadiazole¹ as potent central nervous system, cardiovascular and antiinflammatory agents prompted us to study the pharmacological action of the title compounds.

The synthesis of 2-thio-3-(substituted-aminomethyl)-5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole was carried out as shown in Scheme 1. The intermediate 3 was synthesised by the action of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide with carbon disulphide in

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) (a) EtOH/H₂SO₄, (b) NH₂NH₂.H₂O, (c) CS₂/KOH-EtOH, (d) HCHO/R₁R₂NH.

the presence of ethanolic KOH. Compound 3 underwent Mannich reaction in presence of formaldehyde and secondary amines to afford the title compounds (4a-h; Table 1). Spectral data were consistent with the proposed structures of the compound.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4a-h*

Compd. no.		Molecular formula	M.p. °C
4a	N-Methylpiperazino	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₅ S	91
b	Diethyl amino	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ S	96
c	Diethanolamine	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₇ S	94
d	N-Methylanilino	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ S	86
e	N-Ethylanilino	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	92
f	Morpholino	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₅ S	102
g	Piperidino	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₅ S	98
h	N-Phenylpiperazino	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₅ S	101

*Satisfactory C, H and N analyses were obtained.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A60D instrument using TMS as internal standard. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc.

3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide (2): It was prepared by the method reported².

2-Thio-5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (3): A mixture of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid (0.1 mol) and CS₂ (0.1 mol) in ethanolic KOH (75 ml/0.15 mol) containing water (15 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 24 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the solution poured on crushed ice, acidified with glacial acetic acid and the resulting solid was recrystallised from dimethyl formamide, m.p. 122°; ν_{\max} 1 600—1 610 (C=N), 3 140—3 110 (NH), 1 200 (C=S), 1 550—1 530 and 1 320—1 310 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

2-Thio-3-(substituted-aminomethyl)-5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4a-h): 5-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (3; 0.005 mol) was refluxed in methanol (10 ml) and then formalin (1 ml) and amine (0.005 mol) were added with vigorous shaking. The mixture was cooled, allowed to stand overnight and the solid so obtained was recrystallised from EtOH (Table 1), yields 70—75%; ν_{\max} 1 600—1 610 (C=N), 1 445—1 435 (C—O—C), 1 200 (C=S), 1 550—1 530 and 1 320—1 310 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); 4h δ 6.80—7.32 (8H, m, ArH), 5.02 (2H, s, N-CH₂-N) and 2.32—2.69 (8H, m, 2 × CH₂-N-CH₂).

Biological activity: Toxicity and gross CNS activity were tested according to the reported method³. All the compounds were screened for cardiovascular activity in cats (3—4 kg) of either sex, anaesthetised with sodium pentobarbital (35 mg/kg i.p.). Adrenaline hydrochloride (1 mg/kg), acetylcholine chloride (0.1 mg/kg) and histamine acid phosphate (0.1 mg/kg) were used as standards.

Anti-inflammatory activity was tested on albino rats of either sex weighing 100—160 g using carrageenin-induced oedema⁴. The test compounds (100 mg/kg) were also administered orally. Phenylbutazone (30 mg/kg) was used as the standard.

All tested compounds were found to be non-toxic and psychotropic in nature. LD₅₀ values

NOTES

were 1000 (mg/kg) and above. Most of the compounds are CNS stimulant (4a, b) or depressant (4f-h). Compounds 4c-e increased the spontaneous motor activity and reactivities to sound and touch at the dose 464 mg/kg (i.p.).

CVS activity results indicated that most of the compounds tested at dose of 1.0 and 5.0 mg/kg⁴ exhibited only a mild effect. It was further observed that introduction of *N*-methylpiperazino group was possibly responsible for the marked CVS activity of compound 4a.

The results of the anti-inflammatory activity showed inhibition against carrageenin-induced oedema ranging from 24-11% in rat at 1/10 of their LD₅₀ doses by compounds 4d, g, h. The inhibition of 24% oedema by compound 4h may be attributed to the presence of piperidino moiety.

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